

EASTERN THINKERS' VIEWS ON NATIONAL FOLK GAMES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FORMATION OF A CHILD'S PERSONALITY

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Annotation : This article covers folk games, as well as the opinions of eastern thinkers about the influence of folk games on the formation of a child's personality.

Key words : folk games, Eastern thinkers, Mahmud Kashgari, Alisher Navoi, Sports competitions, Cross-crossing, "Kesak kuydi", "Flogged", "Musht went", Kaikovuz, Umar Khayyam, Qabusnoma, Baburnoma, Amir Temur's tricks, game, movement, Devonu dictionary Turkish , "Chavgon".

It is known that the great children of every nation studied the customs, principles of living, history of their nation and were able to see the prospects of the future. For the first time in the history of Uzbek folk games, the examples of national games were described and described by Mahmud Kashgari, one of the encyclopedic scholars. 1000 years ago, for 6 years, he lived in the area from Turkestan to Termiz, from the shores of Khazar and Arol to the foothills of Tangritog, the history of the Turkmen, Oghiz, Chigil, Yagmo, Kyrgyz and other Turkic-speaking peoples, lands. geography, clan, tribe, linguistic characteristics of peoples, written and oral literature, livelihood methods of nomadic ungulates, shepherds, shepherds, sedentary farmers, gardeners and artisans, word pronunciation and Turkish studied the terms of words in depth and created

"Devon-u-lugatit turk", i.e. "Devon of Turkish words". Mahmud Kashgari, who loved his people, his homeland, appreciated its linguistic and cultural-spiritual wealth, celebrated the holidays, celebrations, traditions, paintings and rituals, daily activities, songs and dances of various tribes. Benazir was keenly interested in her activities and religious beliefs and left all these values as a valuable legacy for future generations. About 150 folk games are mentioned in Devon, and about 20 of them are described in detail.

The emergence and development of Uzbek folk games researching the material and spiritual heritage left by the great thinkers of the East, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud Kashgari, Kaikovus, Omar Khayyam, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, Zainiddin Mahmud Wasifi and other noble people, as well as the physical , cultural theory and implementation is an actual problem waiting for its solution.

The scientist describes the types of competition, focusing on the types of games that are suitable for the age aspects of adults and children. He carefully studied the game, dividing it into both physical and mental exercises. It can be seen from this that many of the modern sports games existed in those times, that is, in the 11th century.

The expression we use now as "Sports competitions" ¹is given by Mahmud Kashgari's divan with the term "dispute". Such a " dispute ". types a lot the statement that it was done _ For example , in hunting debate to do , bow and arrow shoot , bird and animals to hunt , as well as to throw stones on ropes , planks , fences , high hanging placed pumpkin to the destination take shoot dispute . This is Gold it was called the game of pumpkin .

In Devon such of arguments the rule and conditions , methods , results _ to be given prizes , medals equipment , special terms in detail statement done _ It is known that Chavgon is Middle Asia of their peoples very ancient and favorite the

¹ Alikulov H., Omonboeva R., Jami and Davani about education and training. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1998, - 60 p.

horse sports from the games one is considered Grass on hockey o' yini in ancient times guys the horse on long , tip with a curved , leafy " kluchka " . played of the game present it looks like .

Games have an ancient and rich history like the people themselves. The Turkish language scientist Mahmud Kashgari gives valuable information about the naming of folk games and the composition of their playing in his work "Devonu lug'otit turk".

The information given by Kashgari shows that the games have a historical background and basis. In fact, the names of the games and the composition of the games have been passed down from generation to generation. The question arises, what kind of games were there?

"Devonu Lugatit Turk", which is considered the masterpiece of the Uzbek people, provides important information about games. Unfortunately, the old game titles have not been implemented, the order of the games has not been restored. It is of great importance to restore and apply the name of the games mentioned in the Qosh gary dictionary and its order . After all, games are an integral part of national culture. The names of many games are listed in "Devonu Lugatit Turk". The procedure for playing some games is given in detail. Nowadays, children love to play games like nuts and bolts.

It was also popular in the 10th-12th centuries. The current name of this event is "Devonu Lugatit Turk", which contains the names of several events directly related to the nut game. Information about "Chavgon" can be found in the works of A. Navoi, Babur, and other classics. Firdausi's "Shokhnoma" tells a story about a chavgon.

M.Koshgari states that the name of the game is derived from the name of the stick used to hit the chavgon ball. C h avghan chopi is called by this name and is a Persian-Tajik word. Its meaning is "a long stick with a curved end". One of the children's favorite games from the Russian dictionary is the game called "Quotation game", that is, fourteen. Four gates will be built on the ground like a

fortress. It is played by throwing round stones or nuts through these doors. The gameplay of this game is similar to the mak-mak mobile games that children play today. In the past, one of the games that adults and children loved to play was the ball game.

The name of the ball is given as tariq in the Qoshqari dictionary . Koptok was mostly played by Turkish people. At the beginning of the game, the one who hits the ball hard with the fork of the stick starts the game. In the old days, there were no rubber balls. Of course, our creative people used to play with beautiful balls made of wool and silk fabric (which were not, of course, our creative people). Cow, camel, horse wool was considered the best raw material for making balls. There were many types of ball games. Mungiz is a children's game called Mungiz. Children sit around a pit that is not deep into the ground.

Mahmoud Kashgari gives a complete description of the specific rules of the game of chavgon, the definition of the size and border of the field, the gates, the size of the ball, its size, what it is made of, and other features. That is why Chavgon game is a national sport that prepares young men to feel at ease while riding a horse, to be able to handle it, and to perform various movements on it with agility and wrist strength. . Especially, since the game of chavgon is one of the necessary physical exercises in the defense of the country, it focuses on the level of prizes given to the winner of the game. Also, in the Divan, there is a description of such "disputes" as horse racing, chasing, fast standing, climbing, and descending. Water competitions are also worth special attention. Diving, which is one of the water sports, is one of the very ancient professions, and two types of water sports are found in Devon:

- the first is bathing in water, diving, swimming through water, wading through water, chasing in water, throwing something into the water, for example, a piece of wood that does not sink in water;

•the second is games in the sense of fun, recreational activities. These are: pouring water or milk, throwing a flat stone over the water to each other, that is, arguing. Current at the time children they play it as the " cream " game . In the game of the stone to water how many times touching jump " cream " yield to do attention is taken and who produce a lot of cream if he does , that's it winner is counted .

In Devon children of games type a lot occurs . Theirs some of them along the way counting passed if , some - one games detail with given . For example : children in the dark If they come and get " Jchuigon " - if it is called " Koragumi " , one gang up second the gang agility with captive their receipts are called "Bandol" . Also called " Jangli-mangli " . game There is also a type. In love game , ball game , shepherd children games , cool games , girls bitch games are also one by one counting passed . That's it period many games of children present period games reminds _ For example , it is called " Transition-transition " . game ,, Cut burned " , "Whipped " , " Fist went to the games like goes _ Amudarya and Syr Darya on the shores of the island near the foothills as well in places streams , creeks , ponds and lake _ on the sides Children's " Muguz - Muguz " . ancient game played _ In Devon ,, White bone " o' yini example as is brought . Alisher Navoi also wrote his "Mahbub ul- Qulub "² in the play " Aksuyak " . definition gives _

Mahmoud Kashgari _ divan in the 11th century done Alisher Navoi's "Mahbub ul - qulub "³ His work dates back to the 15th century written _ Current At that time , children play the game " Aksuyak " . the same that's it the rule based on they play "Aksuyak" game is not only in Central Asia, but also in the world common in many places. This game can be read in the literature on the ethnography of the peoples of the Scandinavian countries of Europe. Even this

² Abdurrahman Jami. Selected works. - T: Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1971. - 354b.

³ Alikulov H., Omonboeva R., Jami and Davani about education and training. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1998, - 60 p.

game is available in Australia. In fact, folk games never know borders. On the contrary, games serve to strengthen the bonds of mutual friendship and blood brotherhood between peoples and peoples.

When Alloma thinks about folk games, he differs from his contemporaries in this regard, he makes a wide and deep observation of each issue and solves the problem with the help of strong logic, vital factors, with the help of his clever mind. That is why his spiritual masterpieces will serve mankind forever, no matter how many years pass by.

In his works, the scientist who dedicated his whole life to the spiritual maturity and physical perfection of a person proved the great importance of folk games, especially physical education, for a person both theoretically and practically. His scientific-theoretical and practical recommendations, instructions and advices in his creative activity are extremely useful in determining the pedagogical directions in the educational process , summarizing his thoughts on folk games and putting them into practice.

Ibn Sina divides physical education, which is one of the folk games, into five main parts, including:

1. Quick actions.
2. Delicate and light movements.
3. Stronger actions.
4. Very strong actions .

5. Special actions for the body. He includes the following in the type of quick actions of physical education , which mainly represent national folk games or some of their elements, for example: mutual attraction ; push with fist; archery; walk fast; javelin throw; leaning on something above; jumping on one leg; fencing; javelin; on a horse walking; shaking both hands while standing on tiptoes, he moves quickly, stretching his arms back and forth.

The scientist does not simply list the types and elements of the child's game game in the activity his it is understood that attention is focused on an object that

is of some importance to a person.

The great judge paid special attention to the treatment of patients suffering from various diseases with the help of various games. recommends gentle and light types of games to those suffering from diseases;

- in purple to fly
 - a boat or on ships walk to do
- Stronger from games while
- the horse and to the camel riding _
 - kajava and to the carts drop off these are including _

" Nightmare " by Kaikovus people between extremely famous was great moral work is considered The work ,, Child maintenance to do said in the mention in chapter people to the games belongs to was data given _

People of games come output , and development circle interesting information from Umar Khayyam's "Navro znama ", Yusuf Khos Hajib's , Kutadgu knowledge ``', Husain Preacher Fituvvatnomayi of Koshifi Sultan or Youthfulness Alisher Navoi's " Khamsa ", " Lisonut-Tayr ", "Mahbub ul- Qulub " , Zayniddin Vasifi's ,, Rare events " , ,, Amir Temurini's ,, Temur tuzuklari " , Zahiriddin From Babur's " Baburnoma " works our study possible _

People games by chance appear was not , ancient our ancestors their that's it to the degree take until they come heavy difficult the way pressing those who passed Each _ period grow up coming young generation physically perfect , mentally mature by doing bring up natural and social necessity was _ Along with the unique historical heritage, art and literature of the nation and people, their traditions and rituals, cultural attitude and moral qualities are included in the system of spiritual values. They play an important role in preserving the identity of the people, in educating the young generation, and in the socialization of the individual. National spiritual values are a factor of improvement of positive moral qualities, elimination of negative vices that hinder the development of the state

and nation.

The analysis of spiritual monuments, customs and rituals in Uzbekistan shows that their origin goes back to very ancient times. Taking this into account, it can be said that spirituality and national spiritual values are of incomparable importance for preserving national identity, restoring historical memory, and instilling a sense of confidence in the future.

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